

LOW CYCLE FATIGUE LIVES OF SiC PARTICLE REINFORCED ALUMINUM COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT: The effects of reinforcement volume fraction on the low-cycle fatigue lives of SiC particle reinforced aluminum composites were investigated using fully reversed plastic strain-controlled testing. The test results on the composites with 13vol.%, 20vol.%, 25vol.% SiCp and their unreinforced aluminum indicate that the composites exhibit inferior strain-fatigue endurance compared to their unreinforced counterpart. The composites and unreinforced materials all fit Coffin-Manson law. Decrease in the strain fatigue lives occurs with increase in the volume fraction of SiCp in composites. The experimental phenomena are discussed in the light of the real average strain in the matrix of the composites. For a composite reinforced by hard, stiff particles in a soft, compliant matrix, the ceramic particles contribute little to the overall deformation because of their high elastic modulus. The majority of the deformation is contributed by the low modulus, soft matrix. Therefore, for a given external straining, the real strain in the matrix in a composite is significantly higher than that in its unreinforced counterpart. The poor strain fatigue resistances of the composites are largely accounted for by consideration of the real strain mechanism.

Key words: composites, low cycle fatigue, fatigue life

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) reinforced by discontinuous reinforcement exhibit superior performance to the unreinforced, monolithic matrix materials, such as high specific strength and high specific modulus[1]. Applications of these composites in the space, aircraft, automobile and recreational industries are growing rapidly during past years[2]. With the engineering applications of MMCs, the fatigue behavior will become critical in design, life-prediction and reliability analysis of the components made of these materials. Therefore, significant effort has been made to understand the fatigue behavior of these materials[3-11]. However, few investigations were conducted to fully understand the inferior low cycle fatigue lives of MMCs in comparison with their unreinforced matrix metals[12].

Potentially, the effect of the ceramic reinforcement on composite cyclic stress response and strain fatigue life are masked by the precipitates in aluminum alloy matrices. Therefore, the present study is to investigate the differences in plastic-strain fatigue lives of SiC particulate reinforced aluminum composites and their unreinforced counterpart at room and elevated temperature. Since the cyclic deformation behavior is highly sensitive to matrix microstructure, commercially pure

aluminum was selected as a matrix material with the object to eliminate precipitates and other factors that usually existed in aluminum alloys.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The SiCp/Al composites respective containing 13, 20 or 25 volume-percent SiC particulate were made by a powder metallurgy method. The SiC particulate, with an average size of $10\mu\text{m}$, were mechanically mixed with the $14\mu\text{m}$ commercially pure aluminum powder. The chemical composition of the aluminum powder is listed in reference[9]. The mixture was then hot compacted and subsequently extruded by 20:1 at 693K into a rod of 16 mm in diameter. The unreinforced matrix aluminum was produced in the same process. The microstructures of the as-extruded composites are shown in Fig.1. The SiC particles in composites were dispersed with some clustering and partially aligned along the extrusion direction. The test specimens were machined from the as-extruded bars with the loading axis parallel to the extrusion direction. The gauge length and diameter of the specimens were 14 mm and 6 mm respectively. The tensile properties of the composites and the unreinforced material at room and elevated temperature are reported in references[9,10]. Samples for transmission electron microscopy examination were cut by linear cutting machine from the gage section of the sample along the gage length. Ion-milling was utilized for the final thinning of the foils. Samples were examined on a JOEL 2000 FX transmission electron microscopy operating at 200 keV. The initial dislocation cell substructures of the pure Al and 20% SiCp composite are shown in Fig.2.

Fatigue tests were performed under a fully reversed plastic-strain control ranging from 1×10^{-3} to 7×10^{-3} on a MAYES mechanical servo-controlled testing system at room temperature and 441 K in air. A triangular wave of the loading was used and the mean strain was zero. The cycling frequency was 0.03 Hz for the first 10 cycles and it was changed to 0.125 Hz for the rest of fatigue life in order to shorten the testing time with no apparent influence on the actual fatigue life. The hysteresis loops were recorded by a X-Y recorder and a computer datum acquisition system simultaneously. An axial clip-on extensometer was used to measure the strain in fatigue experiments. The clip knives were located symmetrically on both sides of the specimen and no bending load was produced. The plastic-strain control of the test was achieved by keeping the width of the hysteresis loop constant manually.

Figure 1. Optical micrographs of longitudinal planes of the SiCp/Al composites, (a)13vol% SiCp, (b) 20vol%SiCp and (c) 25vol% SiCp.

Figure 2. Initial dislocation cell substructures of the (a) extruded aluminum and (b) 20vol% SiCp composite.

FATIGUE LIVES AT ROOM AND ELEVATED TEMPERATURE

The plastic-strain fatigue life of a commercially pure Al and several SiCp/Al composites at room temperature is shown in Fig. 3. In general, the fatigue life of the composite is shorter than the unreinforced Al. Also, the fatigue life of the composite clearly decreased as the volume fraction of SiC particulate is increased from 13 to 25 %. The presence of SiC particulate would hinder the plastic flow of the Al matrix, leading to the accumulation of plastic strain. The strain concentration adjacent to the particle would certainly contribute to the shorter low-cycle fatigue life of the composite. Other factors which led to a shorter fatigue life of the composite might be due to the presence of defects in the composites, such as particle-matrix decohesion and particle fracture, etc. These defects are potential fatigue crack initiation sites.

The plastic-strain fatigue lives of those SiCp/Al composites at 441 K are shown in Fig. 4. It is obvious that the fatigue lives of composites decreased as the SiCp volume fraction increased at elevated temperature. Naturally, the plastic strain-controlled fatigue lives of composites are shortened at elevated temperature in comparison with at room temperature.

The above results clearly show that the resistance against strain fatigue in the composite is inferior to its unreinforced matrix at both room and elevated temperatures. When the composites undertake cyclic loading, the fracture of reinforcing particles, the debonding of ceramic-metal interfaces and the exhausted fatigue endurance of the matrix can result initiation of microcracks[13]. The shorter strain-fatigue lives of the composites can be attributed to the competition and interaction of the above three factors. The higher stress within the SiC particles than the average stress in the matrix, reported by Xu and Watt [14], could lead to fracture of the particles. However, it should be recognized that the “real strain” of the matrix in the composite is higher than that in the unreinforced matrix material for the same applied total strain. For a composite reinforced by hard, stiff particles in a soft, compliant matrix, the ceramic particles contribute little to the overall deformation because of their high elastic modulus. Thus, the majority of the deformation is contributed by the low modulus, compliant matrix. Therefore, the volume of reinforcing particles should be excluded from the gauge section of the composite. The extent of strain for the composite would rise, which would be consistent with the result of

Arsenault and Shi[15] who observed those larger matrix strains in the zones of denser particulate clusters in comparison with areas with fewer particles. The presence of more severe strain deformation in the matrix of the composite ultimately led to the reduction of fatigue life in the composite.

The real average plastic strain of the composite ϵ_{rp} could be obtained by

$$\epsilon_{rp} = \epsilon_p (1 - V_p) \quad (1)$$

where V_p is the volume fraction of the particulates. The measured plastic strain ranges for the composite should be increased in accordance with Equation (1). The Coffin-Manson relationship between the cyclic plastic strain amplitude and the number of reversals to failure for the composite based on the use of real plastic strain becomes

$$\Delta\epsilon_{rp}/2 = \epsilon'_f (2N)^c \quad (2)$$

The relationship between the real plastic strain amplitude $\Delta\epsilon_{rp}/2$ and the fatigue life of composite at room and elevated temperature is also plotted in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 respectively. With this correction, it gets much smaller for the influence of SiCp volume fraction on the fatigue life of a composite both at room and elevated temperature. The real strain fatigue life curves of composites become close to each other and move towards the fatigue curve of unreinforced Al, even almost overlap with it at room temperature. Although the fatigue curve of Al is not available at elevated temperature, the real strain fatigue curves of composites get much closer than that at room temperature, probably due to a better plastic deformation capability of matrix Al when temperature increased. So the poor fatigue resistances of the composites are largely accounted by consideration of the real strain mechanism. Moreover, this concept of the real strain in composites could be applied to other similar situation such as the creep deformation of composites.

Figure 3. Curves of plastic strain amplitude against number of loading reversals to failure for the composites and unreinforced Al at room temperature.

Figure 4. Curves of plastic strain amplitude against number of loading reversals to failure for the composites at elevated temperature.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the investigations, the following conclusions could be reached: The mechanism of real extent of plastic strain in composites substantially contributes to the shorter low-cycle fatigue life of the ceramic particle reinforced metal matrix composites.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was financially supported by the National Science Foundation of China.

REFERENCES

1. M. Taya and R. J. Arsenault, *Metal Matrix Composite Thermomechanical Behavior*, Pergamon Press, (1989).
2. J. E. Allicon and J. W. Jones, in: *Fundamentals of Metal Matrix Composites*, eds. S. Suresh, A. Mortensen and A. Needleman, Butterworth-Heinemann, p.269 (1993).
3. S. Suresh and R. O. Ritchie, *Metall. Trans.*, 13A, 1627 (1982).
4. T. Christman and S. Suresh, *Mater. Sci. Eng.*, 102A, 211(1988).
5. J. K. Shang and R. O. Ritchie, *Acta Metall.*, 37, 2267 (1989).
6. Z. Wang, and R. J. Zhang, *Acta Metall. Mater.*, 42, 1433 (1994).
7. R. J. Arsenault, S. Fishman and M. Taya, *Progress in Mater. Sci.*, 38, 1(1994).
8. Z. G. Wang, N. L. Han and P. L. Liu, in: *Progress in Advanced Materials and Mechanics*, eds. T. Wang and T.-W. Chou, Peking University Press, Beijing, p.848 (1996).
9. N. L. Han, Z. G. Wang and L. Z. Sun, *Scripta Metall. Mater.*, 32, 1739 (1995).
10. N. L. Han, Z. G. Wang and G. D. Zhang, *Composites Sci. Tech.*, 57, 1491 (1997).
11. L. Wang, Z. M. Sun, T. Kobayashi, H. Toda and Z. G. Wang, *Mater. Trans. JIM*, 37, 762 (1996).
12. N. L. Han, J. M. Yang and Z. G. Wang, *Scripta Mater.*, 43, 801 (2000).
13. Z. R. Liu, D. Z. Wang, C. K. Yao and L. Geng, *Mater. Sci. Eng.* 189A, 235 (1994).
14. X. Q. Xu and D. F. Watt, *Acta Mater.*, 44, 801 (1996).
15. R. J. Arsenault, N. Shi, C. R. Feng and L. Wang, *Mater. Sci. Eng.*, 131A, 55 (1991).